

A Study on Women Entrepreneurs of Nagpur City

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Abstract— Women entrepreneurs are those women who think of a business enterprise, initiate it, organize and combine factors of production, operate the enterprise and undertake risks and handle economic uncertainty involved in running it. The focus of the paper is to identify the main entrepreneurial ventures run by women entrepreneurs in Nagpur city. The study proposes to diagnose the problems faced by the women entrepreneurs and the opportunities available to women entrepreneurs in Nagpur city. The study will aid as a base for future studies on women entrepreneurs. Awareness into challenges faced by these women will provide a platform to overcome the difficulties and attain sustainable growth. The findings of the study could be used by the NGOs and financial institutions to examine, support, nurture & develop women entrepreneurs in their activities.

Keywords— Women Entrepreneurs, Enterprise, Risk, Return

I. INTRODUCTION

Women entrepreneurs may be defined as a woman or a group of women who initiate, organise and run a business concern. Schumpeter – “Women entrepreneurs are those women who innovate, initiate or adopt a business activity”.

Government of India – “A woman entrepreneur is defined as an enterprise owned and controlled by a woman having a minimum financial interest of 51 percent of the capital and giving at least 51 percent of the employment generated in the enterprise to women.”

Frederick Harrison – “Any women or group of women which innovates, initiates or adopts an economic activity may be called women entrepreneurship”.

In short, women entrepreneurs are those women who think of a business enterprise, initiate it, organise and combine factors of production, operate the enterprise and undertake risks and handle economic uncertainty involved in running it.

According to Government of India, “A Woman enterprise is the one owned and controlled by a woman having minimum financial interest of 51% of the capital and giving at least minimum 51% of generated employment to women”.

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Features:

1. Most women with small income are likely to become entrepreneurs
2. Women with small facilities are likely to become entrepreneurs
3. A majority of women entrepreneurs are married. With the support of their husband they accepted entrepreneurship.
4. Most spinsters face difficulties in obtaining financial support to start their enterprises.
5. A large number of women with little or no education and training enter into the business field.
6. Many women become entrepreneurs out of economic necessity.
7. Women’s sincerity and hard work is the cause for sustainability and growth.
8. Women entrepreneurs are security oriented rather than growth oriented

In modern days, particularly in India, there is a great need for women entrepreneurs. Several factors are responsible for compelling the women members of the family to set up their own ventures.

These factors suggesting their need can be broadly classified into two groups:

- I) Motivational factors or needs and
- II) Facilitating factors or needs.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A study conducted by International Labour Organization (ILO) (2006) has found four personal and four external factors that influence women entrepreneurs’ success.

Personal factors comprise – (1) motivation and commitment; (2) abilities and skills; (3) ideas and markets; and (4) resources.

While external factors consist of – (1) business development organizations; (2) broader enabling environment; (3) economic/market environment; and (4) socio-cultural context.

The business development organizations factor considers the roles of government, NGOs, private sector, membership organizations and donors.

The broader enabling environment factor mulls over regulations, policies, institutions and processes.

The economic/market environment factor ponders opportunities and threats (e.g., inflation, interest rates, economic trends etc.).

The socio-cultural context factor considers attitudes, aspirations, confidence etc.

Ulrich (2006) has examined five factors and found that all of them influence youth entrepreneurship development. The five factors include – (1) entrepreneurship education and training, (2) socio-cultural, legitimacy and acceptance, (3) access to finance, (4) business assistance and support and (5) administrative and regulatory framework.

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To identify the ventures run by women entrepreneurs in Nagpur city.
2. To know about the reasons to be an entrepreneur.
3. To analyze the problems faced by women entrepreneurs

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design: Exploratory Research
Research Instruments: Questionnaire.
Sources of data: Secondary Sources: Books, magazines, journals and various web sites
Primary Data: questionnaire.
Sampling method: Random Sampling
Data Collection: Both primary and secondary data is collected for the study.
Data Analysis: Pie charts have been used

Limitations:

1. The study is limited to Nagpur city.
2. There was time constraint.

V. DATA ANALYSIS

Majority of the women entrepreneurs are engaged in the activity of running a beauty parlor (32%) followed by those running tailoring shop (26%), Stationery & Gift items (20%), coaching classes (14%), Health club (8%)

2. Problems faced during Start up of Venture

It could be inferred from the above chart that most of the women entrepreneurs faced low self-confidence and financial constraint as major constraint while setting up their business.

3. Factors to be an entrepreneur

Women are engaged in business due to many factors which encourage them to have their own dignity and self-esteem in the society. Self-dependence, career consciousness and self-respect etc., are the key factors which motivate women entrepreneurs to choose a profession as a challenge.

CONCLUSION

Women entrepreneurs are playing a key role in the economic development of any developing country. They have been recognized as an important source of economic growth. Women entrepreneurs are creating new jobs not only for themselves but also for others. They contribute to the economic well-being of the family and communities, women empowerment and reduction of poverty and thus the role of women entrepreneurs in economic development is inevitable. Women entrepreneurs faced many problems in their efforts to develop the enterprise they have established like problems of finance, shortage of raw materials, marketing problems, lack of entrepreneurial skills, family responsibilities etc. But government and non-governmental organizations are coming forward for the growth of women entrepreneurship in India

and around the globe.

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